

Testing Times: The Role of Standardised Tests in Irish Primary Mathematics Classrooms

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The relation of curriculum and pedagogy to social class and academic achievement has long been a central theme in the sociology of education. This study employs a mixed methods design approach (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009) across eight primary school classrooms at second and fifth class level in DEIS and non DEIS schools. A total of twenty-four mathematics lessons were observed, while eighteen mathematics lessons were video recorded. Focus group interviews with children, child questionnaires and drawings were also employed in the data collection. Eight teachers and eight school principals were interviewed. The focus of this paper is to examine how and in what ways primary school teachers react to statutory testing of mathematics. It is assumed that the content of the mathematics curriculum that is taught correlates with what appears in tests. This paper investigates what changes primary school teachers make in both the content of their mathematics lessons and their approach to teaching mathematics as a consequence of national standardised testing.

Keywords: primary mathematics, standardised testing, social class

Introduction

In the field of mathematics education, the issue of privilege and marginalisation has been examined in terms of social class (Atweh et al., 1998; Cooper & Dunne, 2000; Straehler-Pohl & Gellert, 2013; Zevenbergen, 2001; Zevenbergen & Lerman, 2001). Students' learning opportunities are shaped by educational conditions and policies that originate beyond the classroom and often beyond the school. Student's lack of mathematical proficiency is, in the eyes of policy makers, to be blamed on teachers, within the context of their infrastructure and their institutions, while increased surveillance set within an audit culture, is the order of the day (Walshaw, 2010). With government education policy focused on standards, there is a danger that 'diversity' as constructed in national statistics is understood mainly in its relation to attainment. These somewhat 'uni-dimensional' constructions feed into policy, prompting interventions targeted at low attaining groups such as those in designated disadvantaged contexts. Such policies offer 'an impoverished understanding of difference' and risk perpetuating stereotypes and 'deficit thinking' among teachers (Ainscow et al., 2010; Tang & Ginsburg, 1999).

Students can be unintentionally marginalised in the classroom as a result of unstated norms and power structures, and the factors that shape participation are not limited to conditions inside the classroom. Research on the influence of culture on participation in mathematics classrooms indicates that students who are not enculturated into norms associated with mathematical discourse are at a disadvantage (Atweh et al, 1998; Boaler, 1997; Cooper & Dunne, 2000; Lyons et al., 2003). According to Cobb (2001)

"students' home communities can involve differing norms of participation, language, and communication, some of which might actually be in conflict with those that the teacher seeks to establish in the classroom" (p.471).

Success in the mathematics classroom requires cultural knowledge that can serve to privilege the middle class or those who are the linguistic majority (Lerman & Zevenbergen, 2004; Zevenbergen, 2000). Communication norms associated with mathematics can be a source of ‘cultural confusion’ for students, either restricting participation or weakening the intended benefits of such participation (Rousseau & Tate, 2008). Students’ participation in the mathematics classroom is influenced by organisational and social structures.

Standardised Tests

Research into standardised testing highlights the extent to which these tests influence what knowledge is taught, the form in which it is taught, and how it is taught (Au, 2010; Harlen, 2007, O’ Leary et al., 2019). When student test results are used in accountability systems, teachers and schools will perceive the no-stakes, standardised tests to be high stakes. Teachers begin to view themselves and their effectiveness as teachers of mathematics on the basis of student outcomes on tests. Consequently when such tests are perceived to be high stakes for teachers and schools, the assessment system risks succumbing to teaching to the test, narrowing of the curriculum, teacher cheating and student exclusion (Anagnostopoulos, 2005; Lam & Bordignon, 2001; MacRuairc, 2009a, 2011; McNeil, 2000; Morris, 2011).

Bernstein’s theory of educational transmission is useful in understanding the testing regime in Irish primary mathematics classrooms. For Bernstein (1971), school standardised testing regimes are based upon a visible pedagogy which is realised through strong classification and strong frames and it is this type of pedagogy which transmits symbolic property. As a result schools are directly comparable as to their successes and failures. If student access to visible pedagogy is delayed for too long, examination success may be considered to be in danger. The research of Cooper and Dunne (2000), Anthony and Walshaw (2007) and Lubienski (2002) shows solidarity with Gee (1996) and his argument that students from disadvantaged groups are less likely to adopt the preferred discourse of the classroom because it conflicts with their home or community-based discourse. The corollary of this is that students who are not able to adapt to the discourse of mathematics education, which includes assessment, are more likely to be marginalised from that community. The key role played by language in mathematics education and assessment is succinctly summarised by Durkin and Shire (1991):

Mathematics education begins and proceeds in language, it advances and stumbles because of language, and its outcomes are often assessed in language (p.3).

The difference in performance in mathematics has the potential to influence a student’s future opportunities. The negative impact of standardised testing is notable in schools succeeding in connecting curricula and teaching to the realities of students’ cultures, backgrounds and economic conditions (MacRuairc, 2009a; McNeil, 2000). According to Au (2008) high stakes tests serve to reproduce dominant social relations in education. Bourdieu (1973) and the three key concepts – field, habitus and capital, and their complex interactions, help to illuminate issues of domination and reproduction in education. Capital plays an important role in the relationship between field and habitus. While Bourdieu (1986) describes two main forms of capital (economic and symbolic), this research study into mathematics classrooms will focus on cultural and linguistic capital (a form of symbolic capital). Grenfell (2008) describes cultural capital as a synonym for status or position, and resources that one brings to the field.

School success is predicated on such cultural capital so that middle class students who are familiar with the dominant culture will perform better academically while the mismatch between home and school cultures serves to disadvantage working-class young people. Bourdieu (1990) describes the middle classes as having a better ‘feel for the game’. In the case of high stakes testing, the ‘rules of the game’ are set by the standardised nature of the assessment and, in many cases, by a standardised curriculum, which privileges certain kinds of knowledge. Middle class students can be expected to ‘produce’ the correct kind of knowledge within an examination. Social fields are often not level playing fields and those who begin the game with particularly valued forms of capital and “well-informed” habitus are always at an advantage. In schools and education, it is clear how and why those who have a privileged position and have learned how to play school well, have an investment in maintaining and reproducing the operations of the field.

Standardised testing, streaming/tracking systems in schools for mathematics and pronounced differentiated teaching practices in this subject, as well as other gate-keeping controls, ensure that a differentiated hierarchy of access is produced that emulates, assists, (re)produces, and is (re)produced by the hierarchy within capitalist relations of production. Mathematics high status in the “social division of labour of discourses” (Bernstein, 2000) within schools and society, makes it a high stakes game to play, and its “strong grammar” (Bernstein, 2000) provides it with significant cultural cache for those with the luck and privilege to have access to it as knowing subjects and citizens (Swanson, 2010 p.249). There is a notable absence of debate in Ireland in relation to the impact of a policy of mandatory testing on children from working class, marginalised communities (MacRuaire, 2009a). MacRuaire (2009b) argues that there is an inadequate consideration of the complexity and diversity of issues entrenched in the term ‘educational disadvantage’ when it comes to policy. Many of the initiatives and policies that underpin them are strongly positioned within a functionalist, meritocratic perspective (MacRuaire, 2009a). Targets included in many policy documents are ‘hopelessly aspirational’, preventing the setting of more measured, attainable targets (MacRuaire, 2009b). Standardised testing can lead to a loss of motivation among teaching staff and poor results, particularly in schools designated as disadvantaged.

Methodology

Going inside mathematics classrooms, observing, listening and speaking with research participants, offers invaluable insights into how mathematics is taught, learned and assessed. This study employs a mixed methods design approach (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009) across eight primary school classrooms at second (7 and 8 year olds) and fifth class level (10 and 11 year olds). To allow for comparative analysis of social contexts, it was necessary to enlist two DEIS schools and two non DEIS schools at both second and fifth class level. All eight schools were co-educational. Pseudonyms were used for the research schools and participants. Semi-structured interviews were employed when exploring teachers’ experiences of and attitudes towards standardised testing. Class profiles were created based on the standardised test scores provided by the research schools.

Table 1

Overview of Research Schedule

Time period	Activity
September	Piloting of Children Questionnaire & Visiting the research schools
October	Observation visits to schools and focus group interviews
November	Teacher Interviews (6 female, 2 male)
February	School Leader Interviews (4 male, 4 female)

Table 2

Overview of Research Methodology

	Data Collection Instrument	N	Analytical Approach
Quantitative Instrument Design	Child Questionnaire	164	Quantitative Analysis in SPSS
Qualitative Instrument Design	Classroom observations	24	Thematic Analysis in Nvivo
	Interviews with Children	40	Thematic Analysis in Nvivo
	Interviews with Teachers	8	Thematic Analysis in Nvivo
	Interviews with School Leaders	8	Thematic Analysis in Nvivo

Findings and Discussions

Across the four DEIS schools in this study standardised tests are identified as a key source of challenge and discomfort for teachers. According to these teachers pupils appear to be deficit in the adequate levels of literacy and understanding in order to function in the test:

“I think the language of the maths standardised test is a problem for them. They have to read it, understand the words and then figure out what they have to do. It is asking an awful lot”, (Ms Jones, 2nd Class, DEIS).

The social and linguistic differences among pupils is frequently cited among teachers:

“when my own children went through school standardised tests were easy for them because it’s their language...disadvantage is a totally different ball game and the standardised tests are not easy for them” (Ms Keane, 5th Class DEIS).

This study found that teachers perceive school success to be predicated on cultural capital so that middle class students who were familiar with the dominant culture performed better academically while the mismatch between home and school cultures served to disadvantage students in DEIS schools:

“I used to think it was unfair when I taught in a disadvantaged school...you worked your butt off and then you would do the standardised tests and ...you just wanted to stick your head in the oven” (Caitriona, Non DEIS).

Teachers in this study frequently made reference to pupils being ‘upset’ with their confidence ‘knocked’ and feeling negatively towards mathematics. According to one second

class teacher she felt ‘sorry’ for the pupils who reported finding the test “too hard and I didn’t understand it” (Ms Cooper, 2nd Class, DEIS). A negative construct of pupil ability is shaped by the test, not alone confined to second class but also shared among fifth class pupils:

“you hear them asking each other what Sten they got and if one said a Sten of 2 and someone else said a Sten of 5 or a Sten of 6...you can see them ranking themselves ability wise based on how they compare with their peers..yeah it is hard for them” (Ms Keane, 5th Class, DEIS).

Assessment is a powerful tool in mathematics classrooms. For both second and fifth class teachers in this study, particularly in DEIS schools, teaching goals focused on improving test scores for their pupils. According to teachers in DEIS schools, the testing experience is one of struggle with the linguistic challenges that the test presents. In these schools classroom instruction focused on trying to address the literacy skills necessary for testing as well as the mathematical skills. Practice in test-taking skills was a routine classroom activity. Pressure associated with standardised tests was not felt equally by all schools. The influence of testing on the culture of the school was strongly found among DEIS schools rather than their middle class counterparts who displayed immunity to such pressure. For some teachers in DEIS schools pressure was something they put on themselves as well as what was imposed externally through the impact it was having on their pupils and how pupils in turn viewed themselves as learners of mathematics.

Conclusion

Assessment is an essential tool in both teaching and educational accountability. At the same time there is a strong need to place testing in its proper context and to be realistic of its strengths and weaknesses. Furthermore, there needs to be a greater understanding of the centrality to good teaching and to students’ progress of assessment for learning which is intrinsic to pedagogy rather than detached from it (Alexander, 2010). There is a responsibility on those who develop national standardised tests, and upon those who advise and guide them, to attempt to ensure that the tests fully reflect not only the wide mathematical content that is in a national curriculum, but also that the nature and mode of assessment matches the philosophy of learning and teaching mathematics which occurs in classrooms.

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